

Integrated germplasm improvement—irrigated

Rajavadlu and Sagar-Samba released in Andhra Pradesh, India

M. Kashikar, N. V. Nanda, V. Hasan, and N. Kulkarni, Rice Section A, Agricultural Research Institute, Rajendranagar, Hyderabad 500030, India

Rajavadlu (RNR99377) and Sagar-Samba (RNR52147) were released in Andhra Pradesh (AP) for general cultivation during 1993.

Rajavadlu, a derivative of the cross Rajendra/IR30, is a semidwarf, medium-duration variety with multiple resistances and high yield potential.

In yield trials under transplanted irrigated conditions from 1980 to 1991, Rajavadlu yielded an average of 6.5 t/ha, with 21% higher yields than Tellahamsa, 34% than Saleem, 55% than Prakash, and 24% than Samba-Mahsuri, one of the most popular varieties in AP.

In the All-India Coordinated Trials, Rajavadlu ranked 2nd and yielded an average 21.2% more than check varieties. In farmers' field trials, it yielded an average of 20% more than the checks.

Rajavadlu is nonlodging, photoperiod-insensitive, and fertilizer-responsive. It has 130-135 d duration in wet season and 145-150 d in dry season due to the region's low temperatures. It is resistant to blast, brown spot, and sheath rot and moderately resistant to bacterial leaf blight and gundhi bug. Seedlings up to 50 d old may be planted without problems. Grain is long and slender with white translucent kernels and good cooking quality.

Sagar-Samba (RNR52147) is another medium-duration nonlodging variety with multiple resistances and fine grains. It is derived from the double cross IR8/Siam 29//IR8/Ptb21.

It was tested in various yield trials under transplanted irrigated conditions from 1974 to 1991. Yield averaged 5.7 t/ha—13.4% higher than that of Samba-Mahsuri. In All-India Coordinated and multilocation trials, Sagar-Samba yielded an average of 5.6 t/ha, an average of 12.4% more than that of check varieties.

In large-scale demonstration trials from 1982 to 1991, Sagar-Samba yielded an average of 4.9 t/ha. In minikit trials, it averaged 4.5 t/ha, an 8.3% increase over the checks.

Sagar-Samba is a dwarf photoperiod-insensitive, fertilizer-responsive variety

with a 145 d duration in wet season. It is resistant to blast, sheath rot, brown spot, and gall midge and has field resistance to brown planthopper. Grain is medium slender. ■

Pakhal: a high-yielding, short-duration rice variety for Hazara division in Pakistan

M. Akram, M. Ashraf, F. M. Abbasi, and M. A. Sagar, National Agricultural Research Centre, Islamabad, Pakistan

Pakhal (IR28128-45-2) is a new high-yielding rice variety recommended for cultivation in Hazara division. It is semidwarf and 104 cm tall, compared with local variety JP5, which is 131 cm. Pakhal matures 16 d earlier than JP5. The new variety produced 28% more grain

Table 1. Performance of Pakhal in yield trials. Pakistan, 1988-90.

Year	Yield (t/ha)		Percentage increase over JP5
	Pakhal	JP5	
1988	3.7	2.9	29
1989	5.5	4.4	25
1990	5.0	3.9	28
Mean	4.7	3.7	27

Table 2. Comparative characteristics of Pakhal and JP5. Pakistan.

Agronomic trait	Pakhal	JP5
Plant height (cm)	104	131
Maturity period (d)	124	140
Yield (t/ha)	4.6	3.3
1,000-grain weight (g)	22.9	24.2
Grain quality (physicochemical characteristics)		
Rough grain		
Length (mm)	10.0	7.8
Breadth (mm)	2.2	4.2
Milled grain		
Length (mm)	6.6	5.8
Breadth (mm)	1.9	3.0
L-B ratio	3.5	1.9
Grain size and shape	Long/slender	Short/bold
Head rice recovery (%)	58.8	55.2
Aroma	None	None
Protein content (%)	8.0	7.8
Amylose content (%)	24.7	17.7

than did JP5 in 1989 and 1990 national uniform rice yield trials (Table 1).

Pakhal is resistant to stem borer and leafhopper. Head rice recovery is 58.8% for Pakhal and 55.2% for JP5 (Table 2). Pakhal's grain is long and slender while that of JP5 is short and bold. Pakhal's quality index value is 2.2; that of JP5 is 0.84. ■

ADT42: a new high-yielding, early-duration rice for Tamil Nadu, India

A. P. M. K. Soundararaj, S. Giridharan, S. Geetha, P. Narayanasamy, A. Abdul Kareem, S. Palanisamy, and S. Chelliah, Tamil Nadu Rice Research Institute (TNRRI), Aduthurai 612101, India

ADT42 is a semidwarf indica rice that was developed at TNRRI by pedigree selection from the cross AD9246/ADT29. It is suitable for cultivating as a transplanted crop in the irrigated ecosystem.

In 91 trials conducted at research stations and in farmers' fields in Tamil Nadu, ADT42 yielded a mean of 5.5 t/ha, 10% more than the yield of check IR50 (Table 1).

ADT42 possesses moderate resistance to blast and brown planthopper (BPH) (Table 2).

This variety is 90 cm tall and has a growth duration of 100 d. The grain is long and slender, with good cooking quality. It has hulling recovery of 81.9% and milling recovery of 75.6%. Its 1,000-grain weight is 24.8 g.

ADT42 was released in Jan 1994 for cultivation during kharif season (Jun-Sep) in all districts of Tamil Nadu. ■